

NODULAR RETINAL GLIOSIS IN CONGENITAL MICRO-OPHTHALMIA

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ABSTRACT

Retinal gliosis is a rare benign proliferation of retinal glial cells, which may develop insidiously or in previously diseased eyes. Microphthalmia is a rare developmental condition in which one or both eyes are abnormally small. It may occur as an isolated finding or as part of a systemic disease or syndrome. This case was diagnosed in the department of Pathology at Princess Iman Laboratory and Research Center in October 2022 as nodular retinal gliosis in congenital phthisis bulbi in a 12-year-old female patient, who was born with a microphthalmic eye and underwent eye replacement with a prosthetic eye. This case is reported due to the rarity of both pathological findings presented.

KEYWORDS: Retina, Gliosis, Phthisis bulbi, Microphthalmia.

INTRODUCTION

Retinal gliosis is a rare intraocular lesion that results from the abnormal growth and proliferation of glial cells. It typically occurs as a response to intraocular insults or conditions, such as congenital malformations, intraocular neoplasms, trauma, surgery, retinal detachments or holes, as well as medical conditions like glaucoma and chronic inflammatory diseases. These lesions can present as single or multiple retinal nodules.

This condition is often misdiagnosed as an intraocular neoplasm, which may lead to an incorrect treatment plan. The presentation of retinal gliosis generally includes reduced visual acuity due to retinal folding during disease progression.

Differential diagnoses include intraocular disorders such as uveal melanoma, astrocytic hamartoma, intraocular glioma, retinal hemangioblastoma, intraocular metastases, and other primary disorders of intraocular structures. Glial cell proliferation typically occurs slowly after an intraocular insult or in the presence of chronic disease, often taking more than 10 years.

Diagnosis is usually suspected based on retinal examination in correlation with the patient's medical history or incidentally during histopathological examination of the retina following resection due to these nodules or for another cause.

Techniques that aid in diagnosis include slit-lamp microscopy and spectral-domain optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT), which uses infrared light to measure the retina and visualize its structures and layers.

Treatment for retinal gliosis can be either medical or surgical. Ophthalmologists may use medical treatments to slow the progression of gliosis or prevent its occurrence in high-risk patients. Surgical treatment typically involves membrane removal through pars plana vitrectomy.

CASE REPORT

This report describes a 12-year-old female patient who was born with a microphthalmic eye. The cause of the microphthalmia could not be determined, and there was no family history of similar conditions or other ophthalmic diseases. The patient began to express concern about the appearance of her eye as she got older.

In recent years, she also started experiencing recurrent mild headaches. As a result, the family decided to visit an ophthalmologist to investigate the cause of the headaches and explore the possibility of replacing the non-functional eye with a prosthetic one.

Upon examination, her left eye appeared normal, with normal visual acuity. Slit-lamp microscopy revealed signs of phthisis bulbi, including scarring and end-stage changes in the eye, and enucleation was performed.

Upon receiving the non-functional eye in formalin, the laboratory properly identified the specimen and patient. The specimen was left overnight for fixation. The next day, macroscopic examination revealed a distorted, abnormally small eye with rough retinal tissue. White to gray nodules and plaques were noted on the retina. Representative sections were taken from these nodules, as well as from other areas of the retina and eye

structures. The sections were processed into Hematoxylin and Eosin slides for microscopic examination.

Microscopic examination confirmed the diagnosis of phthisis bulbi, and the nodules and plaques exhibited abnormal, bland-looking proliferation of cells of unknown nature. These cells were oval to spindle-shaped, with fibrillary eosinophilic cytoplasm arranged in sheets. No atypia, necrosis, or mitotic activity was identified.

Immunohistochemical studies were performed to determine the nature of the proliferation. The lesion reacted strongly and diffusely with S-100, GFAP, and NSE immunostains but did not react with EMA. The final diagnosis was benign retinal gliosis in the background of phthisis bulbi.

A, B: Hematoxylin and Eosin slides, C: NSE, D: GFAP, E: Ki67, F: S-100, G: EMA, H: P53

CONCLUSION

Retinal gliosis is a rare condition that is important to recognize, as it is often mistaken for other intraocular neoplasms that may require more invasive treatments. Additionally, thorough macroscopic and microscopic examination of eye specimens is crucial for accurate diagnosis, even in cases where the specimen is sent for another cause, as in the case of phthisis bulbi presented here.

Conflict of Interest: None.